

Lidar Wind Preview Quality Estimation for Wind Turbine Control

Feng Guo¹ and David Schlipf¹

Abstract—Lidar-assisted wind turbine control has been proven to be beneficial for wind turbines. This technology uses the preview of rotor-effective wind speed obtained from lidar measurements in front of the wind turbine. The wind preview allows the controller to react to the disturbance prior to the impact on the turbine. However, the quality of the wind preview provided by a lidar is constantly changing mainly with atmospheric conditions and usually only the lower frequency components of the signal can be used for control. Thus, it is necessary to estimate the wind preview quality online and accordingly adjust the filter parameters to remove the uncorrelated information and to schedule controller parameters. Previously, the wind preview quality during short field testing campaigns has been identified offline prior to using the lidar signal for control. This was done with a frequency-based correlation study by comparing the rotor-effective wind speed estimated from turbine data to the one provided by the lidar. An online application of the frequency-based correlation study however is hard to implement due to the limitation of the estimation from turbine data, the amount of data necessary, and the sensitivity of the frequency-based method itself. In this paper, we develop a new statistic-based method to estimate the wind preview quality by only using the data from a pulsed lidar system without the need of wind turbine data. The method is assessed using simulated lidar measurement scanning an unfrozen wind field. The results show that the method is able to distinguish the preview quality under different wind evolution conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lidar (Light Detecting And Ranging) is able to provide a preview of the rotor-effective wind speed (REWS) in front of the wind turbine, which allows the controller to react to the disturbance prior to the impact on the turbine [1], [2]. However, the REWS detected upstream usually is different from the rotor-effective wind speed that the turbine experiences and the decay of correlation between upstream and downstream measurements is often reflected by the longitudinal coherence in frequency domain [3], [4], [5]. The “true” REWS for control purpose is usually approximated by the mean longitudinal wind speed over the rotor plane [6], [7]. Commercial lidar systems are only able to estimate the REWS based on limited measurement points from various measurement distances in front of the rotor. The measurements are also distributed over the rotor plane due to the inclination of the beams. Therefore, the wind preview quality, i.e. the correlation of the true REWS and the lidar-estimated REWS is influenced not only by the longitudinal coherence, but also by the lateral coherence which determine

Fig. 1. Sketch of previous and proposed method on wind preview quality estimation

the correlation of measurements at two positions within the rotor plane. In LES simulations [5] and real application [8], the turbulence coherence structure varies with atmospheric conditions, such that the lidar wind preview quality changes as well.

Previously, the wind preview studies were done mainly with a frequency-based correlation study by analyzing the coherence between REWS of the turbine to the one provided by the lidar [1], [5], [7]. Prior to using the lidar signal for control, the preview quality during short field testing campaigns has been identified offline using turbine and lidar data together [9], [10], as shown by Figure 1. Based on these studies, a filter with parameters only changing with the mean wind speed has been used to filter out the uncorrelated high frequency component of the signal. For a continuous use of Lidar-Assisted Control (LAC), an online assessment of the wind preview quality is important to avoid harmful control action in case that the wind preview quality deviates largely from the expected one. An online application of the frequency-based correlation study however is hard to implement due to the limitation of the estimation from turbine data, the amount of data necessary, and the sensitivity of the frequency-based method itself [11].

In this paper, we develop a new method, as shown by Figure 1, to estimate the wind preview quality by only using the data from a pulsed lidar system without the need of wind turbine data. In a first step, the correlation coefficients between the line-of-sight measurements at various locations are calculated in real time. In a second step, a frequency-

¹Wind Energy Technology Institute, Flensburg University of Applied Sciences, Kanzleistraße 91–93, 24943 Flensburg, Germany
feng.guo@hs-flensburg.de
david.schlipf@hs-flensburg.de

Fig. 2. Sketch of the scan pattern of the selected lidar system and wind field grid.

based model is used to estimate wind model parameters. In the third and final step, the wind preview quality is calculated based on the estimated wind model parameters. The method is tested with fully unfrozen simulated wind fields and lidar measurements under different wind evolution conditions. The results show that the method is able to distinguish the preview quality under different wind evolution conditions.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the selected turbine and lidar model as well as introduces the method we used to simulate and process lidar measurements and generate turbulent wind fields. Also, the calculation of the reference wind preview quality is discussed. In Section III, the wind preview estimation method is presented. Simulation results are illustrated in Section IV. In Section V, we conclude the paper and discuss perspective further work.

II. SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

In this section the simulation environment is presented. We first define our lidar system, wind turbine, and wind model and then describe, how we generated a wind field. The simulation of the lidar measurements are described next. Finally we derive the reference correlation for the estimation.

A. Selected Lidar System and Wind Turbine Model

We chose a typical commercial lidar system. The scan trajectory is illustrated in Figure 2 and Table I summarizes the lidar scan configuration. The lidar system is able to take measurements in several upstream distances and different transverse-vertical positions.

The lidar system is simulated on the nacelle of the 3.4 MW reference wind turbine from IEA Wind Task 37 [12]. Here, only the rotor diameter of 130 m and the hub height of 110 m are considered in the simulations.

TABLE I

SCAN CONFIGURATION FOR THE SELECTED LIDAR SYSTEM.

number of beams	4
beam azimuth-angles [°]	15.0, 15.0, -15.0, -15.0
beam elevation-angles [°]	12.5, -12.5, -12.5, 12.5
measurement distance	40 to 130 m
full scan time	1.0s
pulse width at half maximum	30 m

B. Wind Model

Wind fields for aero-elastic simulations are vector fields with three components (longitudinal, transverse, and vertical). Here we describe the used wind model consisting of the definition of auto-spectra and coherence, which is then used to generate the wind fields.

1) *Spectrum*: The IEC Kaimal spectrum, as defined in [13] is used for this work. Here, we use abbreviations: S_u , S_v and S_w to represent the auto-spectrum of longitudinal, transverse and vertical wind components, respectively. Homogeneous turbulence is assumed which means the spectra are identical in all simulated positions.

2) *Coherence*: In this work, we consider both transverse-vertical coherence and longitudinal coherence of the u component to generate a wind field. The coherence of v and w components are neglected. The IEC Kaimal coherence model is used to define the transverse-vertical coherence and an exponential decay model proposed by [14] is used for the longitudinal coherence model, as defined by (1) and (2), respectively:

$$\gamma_{ij,yz} = \exp\left(-a_{yz} \cdot r_{ij,yz} \sqrt{\left(\frac{f}{\bar{u}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{b_{yz}}{L_u}\right)^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{ij,x} = \exp\left(-\frac{a_x}{2} \cdot r_{ij,x} \cdot \frac{f}{\bar{u}}\right). \quad (2)$$

Here, a_{yz} and b_{yz} are the transverse-vertical coherence decay and shape parameters and a_x is the longitudinal coherence decay of the u component. Further, f is the frequency, L_u is the turbulence length scale and \bar{u} is the mean wind speed. Here, $r_{ij,yz}$ represents the spatial distance of point i and j projected to a transverse-vertical plane, and $r_{ij,x}$ represents the spatial distance of point i and j in longitudinal direction.

It is worth mention that several authors [5], [8] use formulas of the squared coherence. For conformity with the formula in IEC Kaimal model, we use the non-squared formula here. Also, in [5], [8], another shape parameter b is considered in the longitudinal coherence model. For simplicity, we only consider the longitudinal decay parameter a_x .

Similar to [15], [4], for two points i and j separated in both the longitudinal and transverse-vertical directions, the combined coherence is treated as the product:

$$\gamma_{ij,xyz} = \gamma_{ij,yz} \gamma_{ij,x}. \quad (3)$$

C. Wind Field Generation

Wind fields in traditional simulations without simulated lidar systems are usually only generated in the rotor plane using the Sandia (Veer's) method [16]: A spectral model as above defines the auto-spectra of the wind components in each grid point and the coherence between each point and component. The time series of each component in each grid point is then generated by an inverse Fast Fourier Transform, where the amplitudes are defined by the auto-spectra and random phase angles are calculated to correlate each point and component following the coherence from the spectral model.

For the simulation of a lidar system however, we need to simulate the wind components not only in the rotor plane but also in the measurement points, since lidar measures the upstream wind information. A simplified way is to assume Taylor's frozen turbulence [17]. With this frozen turbulence assumption, the turbulence travels unchanged from the upstream measurement location to the rotor with the mean wind speed. In such a case, the coherence of the longitudinal wind component along the mean wind direction at two different longitudinal locations equals 1. The frozen turbulence method tends to overestimate the correlation between the lidar-estimated REWS and the true REWS [15]. To overcome this problem, "unfrozen" turbulence methods have been proposed in several studies [15], [18] to extend the wind field generation to the lidar measurement points.

In this work we followed [15] to generate the unfrozen turbulence wind field. The lidar is assumed to be fixed on the hub height in the center of the rotor disc so that the spatial coordinates of the measuring points are constant. The following section describes how the lidar measurements are obtained from the generated wind field.

D. Lidar Measurement Simulation

For pulsed lidar systems, the line-of-sight (LOS) signal can be approximated by taking the weighted average of wind speeds along the beam [6], [7]:

$$v_{\text{los}} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (x_n u(r) + y_n v(r) + z_n w(r)) f_{\text{RW}}(r) dr, \quad (4)$$

with r the distance along the beam that centred at the measured position. Further, $u(r)$, $v(r)$ and $w(r)$ are the longitudinal, transverse and vertical components of the wind speed along the lidar beam and $[x_n, y_n, z_n]$ is the normal vector of the laser beam. The weighting function f_{RW} is determined by lidar physical proprieties. For the pulsed lidar system considered here, a normalized Gaussian shape weighting function is used, with a pulse width at half maximum of 30 m [19]. In simulation, discrete points along the beam for each measuring point are taken to apply the weighting function. Since the wind fields have been generated without a time shift, we introduced a time shift for the range weighting.

Fig. 3. Flow chart of wind preview quality estimation.

E. Calculation of the Reference Correlation

With the wind field and lidar measurements, the true REWS u_R and the lidar-estimated u_L are calculated by:

$$u_R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i \quad \text{and} \quad u_L = \frac{1}{x_n} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m v_{\text{los},j}, \quad (5)$$

where u_i is the i th u component in the rotor swept area and $v_{\text{los},j}$ is the j th LOS measurement, n is the total number of grid points in the rotor swept area and m is the total number of lidar measurements. Further, x_n is used to reconstruct the longitudinal component from the LOS using the assumption of perfect alignment. Contrary to the dynamic wind field reconstruction in [4], no time shifting is necessary, since no time shift has been introduced in the wind field generation.

Instead of using the coherence in frequency domain [6], [20], the reference wind preview quality is expressed by the correlation coefficient (ρ_{RL}) between the true REWS and lidar-estimated REWS in time domain, which is calculated from the wind field and the lidar measurements by

$$\rho_{\text{RL}} = \frac{\text{cov}_{\text{RL}}}{\sqrt{\text{var}_{\text{R}} \text{var}_{\text{L}}}}, \quad (6)$$

where cov_{RL} is the co-variance between u_R and u_L . Further, var_{R} and var_{L} denote the variance of u_R and u_L , respectively. In the following section we describe how the correlation coefficient can be estimated on lidar measurements only.

III. WIND PREVIEW ESTIMATION

In this section, the step-by-step procedure for wind preview quality estimation is introduced as shown by Figure 3. The first step is to use the historical LOS data at multiple beams and range gates over an analysis period to calculate the correlation coefficient of any LOS pair: ρ_{ij} , the mean wind speed \bar{u} and the yaw misalignment α_H . In step 2, these parameters are considered as input to a model fitting procedure, where an optimization problem is solved to find the coherence decay parameter a_{yz} and a_x . In step 3, the mean wind speed and the yaw misalignment from step 1 and coherence decay parameters from step 2 are used together to calculate the estimated correlation coefficient $\rho_{\text{RL},\text{est}}$.

A. Time Domain Correlation Calculation

For the pulsed lidar system considered in this work, there are 40 measuring positions distributed over 4 beams and 10 measurement distances, see Figure 2. The LOS data of all measuring positions are captured within 1 s and stored in a buffer. Based on the analysis time used in [8], the correlation coefficients ρ_{ij} are calculated from the co-variance cov_{ij} between the LOS signals with a time length of 30 min of point i and j as well as from the respective variances var_i and var_j of the LOS signals:

$$\rho_{ij} = \frac{\text{cov}_{ij}}{\sqrt{\text{var}_i \text{var}_j}}. \quad (7)$$

As shown in Figure 3, mean wind speed and yaw misalignment are also derived from the LOS data with 30 min time length by basic wind field reconstruction [21]. In this paper, the yaw misalignment is neglected in the analysis for simplification and thus the mean wind speed \bar{u} is the mean of u_L over 30 min.

B. Model Fitting

Since the correlation pairs obtained from Step 1 contain the real time correlation information distributed in different spatial positions, it is possible to derive the correlation decay with regard to the increase in spatial separation. The cross-spectrum of two LOS wind speed measured at the i th position and the j th position is derived based on (8), where $\mathcal{F}\{\}$ represents for the Fourier transform operation and $\mathcal{F}^*\{\}$ represents for the conjugate of Fourier transform:

$$S_{\text{los},ij} = \mathcal{F}\{v_{\text{los},i}\}\mathcal{F}^*\{v_{\text{los},j}\}. \quad (8)$$

Detailed expression of (8) can be found in [4].

With the model-based expression of $S_{\text{los},ij}$, the model-based co-variance of i th LOS and j th LOS are approximated by [22]:

$$\text{cov}_{ij,\text{mod}} = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} \text{Re}(S_{\text{los},ij})df. \quad (9)$$

If $i = j$, $S_{\text{los},ii}$ or $S_{\text{los},jj}$ then become the auto-spectrum of LOS at i position or j position, and:

$$\text{var}_{i,\text{mod}} = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} S_{\text{los},ii}df \quad (10)$$

$$\text{var}_{j,\text{mod}} = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} S_{\text{los},jj}df. \quad (11)$$

For (9) to (11), the integration range shall in principle be from 0 to infinite. This is not feasible to achieve due to the limits of data length and data sampling frequency. The minimal frequency f_{\min} used is the frequency determined by analysis time length, i.e. $1/(30 \text{ min})$, and the maximum frequency f_{\max} used is the sampling frequency of the lidar system.

With $\text{cov}_{ij,\text{mod}}$, $\text{var}_{i,\text{mod}}$, and $\text{var}_{j,\text{mod}}$ the model based correlation coefficient pairs $\rho_{ij,\text{mod}}$ are obtained by Equation (7).

An optimization problem is then formulated to find the optimal coherence decay parameter a_{yz} and a_x which minimize the mean-squared error between the model-based correlation

Fig. 4. Example of considered correlation pairs in model fitting.

Fig. 5. The model fitting process at one time step. For the in-plane correlation, spatial separation refers to $r_{ij,yz}$. For the along beam correlation, spatial separation refers to $r_{ij,x}$.

coefficients $\rho_{ij,\text{mod}}$ and the ρ_{ij} from the lidar measurements of Step 1:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize } f \quad \text{with: } f = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m (\rho_{ij} - \rho_{ij,\text{mod}})^2 \quad (12) \\ &\text{subject to} \quad 0 \leq a_{yz}, 0 \leq a_x. \end{aligned}$$

In order to simplify the optimization problem, b_{yz} and other spectral model parameters such as the length scale L_u are considered to be constant in this initial study.

Theoretically, $m \times m$ pairs could be calculated for a lidar that has m measured positions. The computational effort increases significantly with m , but increasing the number of pairs minimizes the impact of outliers. Instead of using all the pairs to solve the optimization problem, we choose the ‘along-beam’ pairs and the ‘in-plane’ pairs to solve (12). An intuitive demonstration of the chosen pairs could be seen in Figure 4. Using these two types of pairs reduces the time spent in solving the optimization problem significantly, while ensures the diversity of pairs.

An example of model fitting at a time step is shown in Figure 5. In the figure, for identical separations, ensemble average is applied to get the ensemble averaged correlation coefficient ρ_{ij} .

Fig. 6. Comparison between estimation and reference correlation. left: weak evolution condition; right: strong evolution condition

C. Frequency Domain Correlation Calculation

With the decay parameters a_{yz} and a_x from step 2 and the mean wind speed \bar{u} from step 1, the estimated correlation coefficient $\rho_{\text{RL,est}}$ between the true REWS and the lidar-estimated REWS is obtained by

$$\rho_{\text{RL,est}} = \frac{\text{cov}_{\text{RL,mod}}}{\sqrt{\text{var}_{\text{R,mod}} \text{var}_{\text{L,mod}}}}, \quad (13)$$

while the model-based co-variance $\text{cov}_{\text{RL,mod}}$ between the true REWS and the lidar-estimated REWS as well as the respective variances are approximated by

$$\text{cov}_{\text{RL,mod}} = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} \text{Re}(S_{\text{RL}}) df \quad (14)$$

$$\text{var}_{\text{R,mod}} = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} S_{\text{RR}} df \quad (15)$$

$$\text{var}_{\text{L,mod}} = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} S_{\text{LL}} df. \quad (16)$$

Here, S_{RL} is the model-based cross-spectrum between the true REWS and the lidar-estimated REWS, S_{RR} is the model-based auto-spectrum of the true REWS, S_{LL} is the model-based auto-spectrum of the lidar-estimated REWS.

Detailed derivation of S_{RL} , S_{RR} and S_{LL} can be found in [6]. However, it is worth to mention that they depend on the auto-spectra S_u , S_v , and S_w and the spatial coherence $\gamma_{ij,xyz}$. Here, S_u , S_v and S_w depend only on the mean wind speed from step 1 and $\gamma_{ij,xyz}$ of any two points is calculated based on the the coherence decay parameters a_{yz} and a_x from step 2 and the mean wind speed.

D. Confidence Bound of Estimation

Due to the irregularity of turbulence, we cannot expect the correlation or coherence of wind speeds pairs between measurements with identical spatial separation to be always

the same [23]. The actual observations usually are distributed around the model. Thus, it is necessary to define a confidence bound of the estimation. Here, we use the model-based correlations in strong and weak evolution conditions to determine a confidence bound as described by:

$$\text{cb} = \frac{1}{2} (\rho_{\text{RL,weak}} - \rho_{\text{RL,strong}}). \quad (17)$$

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

In this section, the results from simulations with weak and strong wind evolution scenarios are presented. These scenarios are defined according to observations by [8], where coherence decay parameters are summarized using real lidar measurements. For weak evolution scenario, the a_x is chosen to be 1. And $a_x = 3.5$ is chosen for strong evolution. The main motivation here is to check whether the proposed approach is able to detect the difference in wind preview quality under different wind evolution scenarios.

For each scenario, a wind field with time length of 1 h and time step of 0.25 s and different random seed is simulated. A time window of 30 min is applied to buffer the LOS signals and apply the proposed estimation procedure. The IEC normal turbulence model for a turbulence class A, a mean wind speed 16 m/s, and the default decay parameter $a_{yz} = 12$ as defined in [13] are used for both scenarios.

The results are shown in Figure 6. For both evolution scenarios, the coherence decay constant a_{yz} and a_x vary with the analyzing time window of 30 min, but the overall mean values are close to the defined values. For weak evolution, ρ_{RL} fluctuates around $\rho_{\text{RL,weak}} = 0.95$ and for strong evolution it varies around $\rho_{\text{RL,strong}} = 0.88$. The estimated correlation coefficient $\rho_{\text{RL,est}}$ generally follows the reference value and stays within the confidence bounds of the reference correlations.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this work, a statistic based method is presented which allows to estimate the wind preview quality in real time by only using the data from a pulsed lidar system without the need of wind turbine data. The method calculates continuously the correlation coefficients between the line-of-sight wind speed from various measurement distances over a certain time window (here 30 min). A spectral model is then used to estimate lateral and longitudinal decay parameters by fitting the modelled coefficients to the measured one. With these parameters and the spectral model, the wind preview quality is provided continuously represented by the correlation coefficient between the rotor-effective wind speed and the lidar estimate of the rotor-effective wind speed, which can be used for feed-forward control.

Overall, the results show that the method is able to distinguish between low and high preview quality using a time window of 30 min. The advantage over the previously used offline estimation of the measurement coherence is that (1) it provides a continuous signal which can be directly used in lidar-assisted control, (2) is based on calculations with low computational effort, and (3) is only based on lidar data itself without the need of processing turbine data.

The method however uses assumptions on the wind turbulence such as the Kaimal model and an exponential decay for the wind evolution.

In future work, we plan to have a more detailed analysis of the method and for example investigate whether adding more parameter to the fitting step can improve the results and if the method still works when wind field parameters such as the length scale are changed. Other approaches, like the Gaussian process regression used by [8] can also be investigated to obtain the coherence decay parameters.

Further, the estimated preview quality can be used in aero-elastic simulations to adjust an adaptive filter for a feedforward controller. The cut-off frequency of a filter can be continuously adapted to avoid undesired control behaviour caused by low preview quality and to fully exploit the benefit of the wind preview under high preview quality. For this purpose, the cut-off frequency of the adaptive filter will be designed as a function of the correlation coefficient.

Finally, a field testing is necessary to prove that this preview quality estimation provides useful results under real conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 858358 (LIKE – Lidar Knowledge Europe).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Schlipf, *Lidar-Assisted Control Concepts for Wind Turbines*. PhD thesis, University of Stuttgart, 2015.
- [2] E. Simley, P. Bortolotti, A. Scholbrock, D. Schlipf, and K. Dykes, "IEA wind task 32 and task 37: Optimizing wind turbines with lidar-assisted control using systems engineering," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1618, p. 042029, sep 2020.
- [3] E. Simley, L. Y. Pao, N. Kelley, B. Jonkman, and R. Frehlich, "LIDAR wind speed measurements of evolving wind fields," in *Proceedings of the 50th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting Including the New Horizons Forum and Aerospace Exposition*, (Nashville, USA), 2012.
- [4] D. Schlipf, F. Haizmann, N. Cosack, T. Siebers, and P. W. Cheng, "Detection of wind evolution and lidar trajectory optimization for lidar-assisted wind turbine control," *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, vol. 24, pp. 565–579, 11 2015.
- [5] E. Simley, "Wind speed preview measurement and estimation for feedforward control of wind turbines," *PhD Thesis*, 2015.
- [6] D. Schlipf, J. Mann, and P. W. Cheng, "Model of the correlation between lidar systems and wind turbines for lidar assisted control," *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, vol. 30, no. 10, pp. 2233–2240, 2013.
- [7] E. Simley, H. Fürst, F. Haizmann, and D. Schlipf, "Optimizing lidars for wind turbine control applications – results from the IEA wind task 32 workshop," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 10, no. 863, 2018.
- [8] Y. Chen, D. Schlipf, and P. W. Cheng, "Parameterization of wind evolution using lidar," *Wind Energy Science*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 61–91, 2021.
- [9] A. Scholbrock, P. Fleming, L. Fingersh, A. Wright, D. Schlipf, F. Haizmann, and F. Belen, "Field testing LIDAR based feed-forward controls on the NREL controls advanced research turbine," in *Proceedings of the 51st AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting Including the New Horizons Forum and Aerospace Exposition*, (Dallas, USA), 2013.
- [10] D. Schlipf, P. Fleming, F. Haizmann, A. Scholbrock, M. Hofsäß, A. Wright, and P. W. Cheng, "Field testing of feedforward collective pitch control on the CART2 using a nacelle-based lidar scanner," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 555, no. 1, p. 012090, 2014.
- [11] F. Haizmann, P. Fleming, D. Schlipf, A. Scholbrock, M. Hofsäß, A. Wright, and P. W. Cheng, "Implementation of an online correlation analysis for an adaptive lidar based feed-forward controller for wind turbines," *EWEA PO.ID 171*, 2013.
- [12] P. Bortolotti, H. C. Tarres, K. Dykes, K. Merz, L. Sethuraman, D. Verelst, and F. Zahle, "IEA wind task 37 on systems engineering in wind energy – WP2.1 reference wind turbines," tech. rep., International Energy Agency, 2019.
- [13] IEC 61400-1, *Wind turbines - Part 1: Design requirements*. International Electrotechnical Commission, 2019.
- [14] R. Pielke and H. Panofsky, "Turbulence characteristics along several towers," *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 115–130, 1970.
- [15] J. Laks, E. Simley, and L. Y. Pao, "A spectral model for evaluating the effect of wind evolution on wind turbine preview control," in *Proceedings of the American Control Conference*, (Washington, USA), 2013.
- [16] P. S. Veers, "Three-dimensional wind simulation," Tech. Rep. SAND88-0152, Sandia National Laboratory, 1988.
- [17] G. I. Taylor, "The spectrum of turbulence," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A - Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, vol. 164, no. 919, pp. 476–490, 1938.
- [18] E. Bossanyi, "Un-freezing the turbulence: improved wind field modelling for investigating lidar-assisted wind turbine control," in *Proceedings of the European Wind Energy Association annual event*, (Copenhagen, Denmark), 2012.
- [19] J.-P. Cariou, "Pulsed lidars," in *Remote Sensing for Wind Energy, DTU Wind Energy-E-Report-0029(EN)*, ch. 5, pp. 104–121, June 2013.
- [20] D. P. Held and J. Mann, "Lidar estimation of rotor-effective wind speed-an experimental comparison," *Wind Energy Science*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 421–438, 2019.
- [21] D. Schlipf, A. Rettenmeier, F. Haizmann, M. Hofsäß, M. Courtney, and P. W. Cheng, "Model based wind vector field reconstruction from lidar data," in *Proceedings of the German Wind Energy Conference DEWEK*, (Bremen, Germany), 2012.
- [22] J. S. Bendat and A. G. Piersol, *Random data; analysis and measurement procedures*. New York, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 1971.
- [23] R. Stull, *An Introduction to Boundary Layer Meteorology*. Atmospheric and Oceanographic Sciences Library, Springer Netherlands, 1988.